

Echoes of the hexagon: non-CHP configurations (supplemental material)

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Abstract

We report the first non-CHP configurations that we have obtained for regular polygons of up to 96 sides (multiples of 6).

1 Introduction

We report the first non-CHP configurations that we have obtained for regular polygons of up to 96 sides (multiples of 6). For large enough systems curved hexagonal packing is not optimal anymore and denser configurations can be obtained by disrupting the regular structure of CHP. For the special cases of $\sigma = 12, 18, 36, 72$ the CHP "survive" up to $N = 127$ (included).

This document is organized as follows: in [sec.2](#) we present the explicit diagrams for *all* the non-CHP configurations that we have calculated; in [sec. 3](#) we present the corresponding Voronoi diagrams.

σ	k	ρ	$\rho - \rho_{CHP}$
12	7	0.838209	0.0109501
18	7	0.826627	0.00687681
24	6	0.818231	0.000477362
30	6	0.817599	0.00137266
36	7	0.825064	0.00798317
42	6	0.817919	0.0017007
48	6	0.816806	0.000371802
54	6	0.816963	0.000313375
60	6	0.816443	0.0000973674
66	6	0.816631	0.000417085
72	7	0.825047	0.00794864
78	6	0.816701	0.000480921
84	6	0.816578	0.000294333
90	6	0.816688	0.000323156
96	6	0.816786	0.000517179

Table 1: Emergence of non CHP configurations

2 Explicit diagrams

Figure 1: Diagrams of non CHP configurations

3 Voronoi diagrams

Figure 2: Diagrams of non CHP configurations

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References

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